

GENERAL CONCEPTS OF LEARNER-CENTRED TEACHING

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Annotation: This article devoted to open general concepts of learner-centred teaching. Moreover, special characteristic features of learning-centred teaching, its advantages and disadvantages of this method were given.

Key words: *Globalize, expository form, pedagogical model, progressive movements, teacher-centered, student-centered approaches.*

Globalized approaches to education are growing in spread and influence, informing the blueprint for educational reforms, forming current instructional practices, and reflecting the paradigm shift in education towards learner-centeredness. Learner-centered education (LCE) is a model that emerged at the turn of the twentieth century to shape a new understanding of learning, and to pave the way for what teaching and learning ought to be like in the new millennium.

The traditional teaching, which is distinguished by its expository form and narrative character, has been the most pervasive pedagogical model around the world. Critique to this model has been developed at different historical moments, and socio-economic and geographical contexts, with different political aims in mind, by various actors such as critical pedagogues from developing countries (e.g., Freire), educationalists in the western world (e.g., Rousseau, Dewey, and Vygotsky) and international organizations involved in education (e.g., UNESCO and UNICEF). Traditional teaching has been criticized for relegating education to an act of depositing whereby teachers make deposits and students receive, memorize, and repeat to the best of their efforts and capacities. Such practices have

also been examined for being ineffective and leading to the acquisition of skills of a lower taxonomic level , for undermining spontaneity and initiative among students and for inhibiting creativity and critical thinking[1]. Early progressive movements proposing alternatives to traditional teaching originated in the second half of the 1800. In the following period, several other dilemmas have been proposed, yet the current discussion is managed by two competing approaches. These are traditional teaching approaches and learner-centered teaching (LCT), constructivism. The former advocate's structure and some directivity in supporting the learning process effectively in school environments, and the second is contrasted with the traditional model.

There are two common learning systems in language teaching, they are teacher-centered and student-centered approaches. In recent years more teachers have moved toward the student-centered approach. In most cases, it is best for teachers to use a combination of approaches to ensure that all students' needs are met. When both approaches are used together, students can enjoy the positives of both types of learning. Instead of getting bored with teacher-centered education or losing sight of their goals in a completely student-centered classroom, learners can benefit from a well-balanced educational atmosphere. The definition of the teacher-centered and student-centered approaches is based on a simple fact: the one who speaks more in class is the center. The students speak more than 50% of the class time - it's a student-centered class.

Teacher-centered approach is a kind of learning system when the teacher becomes a center of the process. The student's role of teacher-centered approach is just to be a good listener. The students just receive the material that is given by the teacher. Student-centered approach includes the idea that students have choice in what to study and how to study. Student-centered learning is focused on the student's needs, abilities, interests, and learning styles with the teacher as a facilitator of learning. Teachers provide the way for students to access the material, so students can easier get knowledge. Teachers also should help them to decide the

purpose that will be achieved by students, encourage them to evaluate their learning, help them to work together in groups, and make sure that they know the way to use the sources and the facility of learning[2]. The students in this approach have the main role, because they become a center of the learning process. The material is not provided by the teacher but students now are researching the material by themselves. In the student-centered approach, students construct knowledge through gathering and synthesizing information and integrating it with the general skills of inquiry, communication, critical thinking, problem solving and so on. In the student-centered approach the students have a role to decide the learning strategy. So, not only the teacher but also the students choose the appropriate learning strategy. The key decisions about learning are made by the students through negotiation with the teacher.

When a classroom operates with student-centered instruction, students and instructors share the focus. Instead of listening to the teacher exclusively, students and teachers interact equally. Group work is encouraged, and students learn to collaborate and communicate with one another. We can define the main principles of student-centered learning as: the learner has full responsibility for her/his learning; involvement and participation are necessary for learning; the relationship between learners is more equal, promoting growth and development; the teacher becomes a facilitator and resource person; the learner sees himself differently as a result of the learning experience.

There are advantages and disadvantages of student-centered learning. As for the advantages we can name the following:

- students learn important communicative and collaborative skills through group work;
- students learn to direct their own learning, ask questions and complete tasks independently;

➤ students are more interested in learning activities when they can interact with one another and participate actively. Now point out some disadvantages:

- because students are talking, classrooms are often busy, noisy and chaotic;
- o teachers must attempt to manage all students' activities at once, which can be difficult when students are working on different stages of the same project;
- because the teacher doesn't deliver instruction to all students at once, some students may miss important facts;
- some students prefer to work alone, so group work can become a bit difficult for them.

There are five characteristics of teaching that make it learner-centered[3].

1. Learner-centered teaching engages students in the hard, messy work of learning. Teachers are doing too many learning tasks for students. They ask the questions, they call on students, they add details to their answers. They offer the examples. They organize the content. They do the preview and the review. In most classes teachers are working much harder than students, they get far more practice than the students.

2. Learner-centered teaching includes explicit skill instruction. Learner-centered teachers teach students how to think, solve problems, evaluate evidence, analyze arguments, generate hypotheses. They do not assume that students pick up these skills on their own, automatically. A few students do, but they tend to be the students most like us and most students aren't that way.

3. Learner-centered teaching encourages students to reflect on what they are learning and how they are learning it. Learner-centered teachers talk about learning. In casual conversations, they ask students what they are learning. In class they may talk about their own learning. They challenge student assumptions about learning and encourage them to accept responsibility for decisions they make about learning. Learner-centered teachers include assignment components in which students reflect, analyze and critique what they are learning and how they are

learning it. The goal is to make students aware of themselves as learners and to make learning skills something students want to develop.

4. Learner-centered teaching motivates students by giving them some control over learning processes. Teachers decide what students should learn, how they learn it, the pace at which they learn, the conditions under which they learn and then teachers determine whether students have learned. Students aren't in a position to decide what content should be included in the course or which textbook is best, but when teachers make all the decisions, the motivation to learn decreases and learners become dependent. Learner-centered teachers search out ethically responsible ways to share power with students. They might give students some choice about which assignments they complete. They might let students set assignment deadlines within a given time window. They might ask students for the help in creating assessment criteria.

5. Learner-centered teaching encourages collaboration. Learner-centered teachers recognize that students can learn from and with each other. Certainly the teacher has the expertise and an obligation to share it, but teachers can learn from students as well. Learner-centered teachers work to develop structures that promote shared commitments to learning[4].

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that teaching within higher education has experienced a pedagogical shift in recent years, with new approaches to improve students' motivation, autonomy and achievement. Student centered learning is a pedagogical approach that takes learning pace of students, the differences in their learning styles, their interests, skills and needs into consideration. Also, the experiences of students, the learning outcomes, active learning tasks, the content and framework for presenting academic material in conducive learning environment is given significance in the student centered learning environments. Educators prudently facilitate a systematic instructional design process by organizing appropriate pedagogical approaches so that learners are provided support and guidance to accomplish skills in self-evaluation and

independence in their learning. In this context, the purpose of the study was to determine the effects of using learner-centered instructional approaches on students' development in vocabulary retention and acquisition.

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